

Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of some Bis-thiazoles and Imidazo[2,1-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazoles

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Manuscript received 13 April 1992, revised 10 September 1992, accepted 4 February 1993

Thiazole¹, imidazole² and thiadiazole³ derivatives are well-known for their varied biological activities. Therefore, it was felt interesting to synthesise fused heterocyclic systems incorporating two of these biologically active moieties in a molecular framework containing substituted indene or 5,6-dihydronaphthalene ring system as rigid conformers of phenylalkyl moiety, with a view to study the additive effect on their biological properties.

2-ylthioureas (**2a, b**) in ethanol¹ furnished the corresponding 2-[*N*-(4-arylthiazol-2-yl)]aminoindeno/tetraleno[1,2-*d*]thiazoles (**3a-f**). The absence of C=S and C=O bands in their ir spectra suggested the cyclisation of **1a-c** and **2a,b** into **3a-f**. Similarly, **1a,b** on condensation with 2-amino-5-aryl[1,3,4]thiadiazoles (**4a-d**) in ethanol⁵ gave 8-alkoxy-2-aryl-7-methoxyindeno[1',2' : 4,5]imidazo[2,1-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (**5a-h**). The absence of C=O and NH₂ bands in their ir spectra suggested the cyclisation of **1a,b** and **4a-d** into **5a-h**.

The antifungal screening of compounds **3a-f** and **5a-h** was carried out against *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus flavus* by the usual turbidity method⁶. A commercial fungicide Dithane M-45 was also tested under similar conditions for comparison. Most of the tested compounds did not show appreciable activity. The antibacterial activity of these compounds was determined in vitro with paper-disc method⁷ against two pathogenic microorganisms, viz. *Escherichia coli* (gram-negative) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram-positive) at 2 and 5 mg ml⁻¹ concentrations in the nutrient agar media. The compounds were not significantly active towards these bacteria.

Experimental

All m.p.s. were taken on a Buchi melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. TLC was performed on silica gel G plates using benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) as irrigant and iodine vapour as visualising agent. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on Varian T-60A and EM-390 spectrometers (60 and 90 MHz) using TMS as internal reference. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

2-*N*-[4-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)thiazol-2-yl)]amino-5,6-dimethoxyindeno [1,2-*d*]thiazole (**3a**): A mixture of 4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)thiazol-2-ylthiourea (0.53 g, 2 mmol) and 2-bromo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one

- 3a**; R = OMe, R¹ = OMe, R² = H, R³ = OMe, n = 1
b; R = OMe, R¹ = OEt, R² = H, R³ = OMe, n = 1
c; R = OMe, R¹ = OMe, R² = OMe, R³ = OMe, n = 1
d; R = OMe, R¹ = OEt, R² = OMe, R³ = OMe, n = 1
e; R = H, R¹ = H, R² = H, R³ = OMe, n = 2
f; R = H, R¹ = H, R² = OMe, R³ = OMe, n = 2
5a; R = R¹ = OMe, R⁴ = C₆H₅, n = 1
b; R = R¹ = OMe, R⁴ = CH₂C₆H₅, n = 1
c; R = R¹ = OMe, R⁴ = (2-Cl)C₆H₄, n = 1
d; R = R¹ = OMe, R⁴ = (4-OMe)C₆H₄, n = 1
e; R = OMe, R¹ = OEt, R⁴ = C₆H₅, n = 1
f; R = OMe, R¹ = OEt, R⁴ = CH₂C₆H₅, n = 1
g; R = OMe, R¹ = OEt, R⁴ = (2-Cl)C₆H₄, n = 1
h; R = OMe, R¹ = OEt, R⁴ = (4-OMe)C₆H₄, n = 1

The synthons 2-bromoindanone/tetralone (**1a-c**) were used for the preparation of the two types of compounds. Thus **1a-c** on reacting with 4-arylthiazol-

(0.542 g, 2 mmol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 0.5 h. After cooling to room temperature, the solvent was distilled off and the residue neutralised with NH₄OH solution. The resulting solid was washed and crystallised from ethanol : acetone (2 : 1), (0.320 g, 34.69%), m.p. 300°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 270 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 560 (C=C), 1 350 (C-N), 1 255 (C-O-C asym), 860 (=C-H bend) and 700 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ 3.9 (9H, s, 3 × OCH₃), 4.04 (2H, s, ArCH₂) and 6.1–8.0 (6H, m, ArH and buried 1H, s, C=CH=S).

All other compounds (yields 25–36%) were prepared by the above procedure : **3b**, m.p. >300°; **c**, 253°; **d**, 261°; **e**, >300°; **f**, 267°.

7,8-Dimethoxy-2-phenylindenol[1',2' : 4,5]imidazo[2,1-b][1,3,4]thiadiazole (5a) : A mixture of 2-amino-5-phenyl[1,3,4]thiadiazole (0.22 g, 1 mmol) and 2-bromo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (0.335 g, 1 mmol) in dry ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled and neutralised with K₂CO₃ solution. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles (0.125 g, 22.7%), m.p. 163°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 592 (C=N), 1 520 (C=C), 1 355 (C-N), 1 240 (C-O-C asym), 850 (=C-H bend) and 655 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ 3.9 (6H, s, 2 × OCH₃), 4.0 (2H, s, ArCH₂) and 7.2–8.3 (7H, m, ArH).

All other compounds (yields 22–39%) were prepared by the above procedure : **5b**, m.p. 119–20°;

c, 155°; **d**, 122–23°; **e**, 168°; **f**, 126°; **g**, 160°; **h**, 128°.

Acknowledgement

The author's thanks are due to Dr. P. Somal, Microbiology Section, R. R. L., Jammu, for antimicrobial activity screening.

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